

ASSIS, Machado. **Mulheres de Machado**. Illustrations Catarina Bessel. São Paulo: SESI-SP, 2017.

REVIEW¹

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Machado de Assis was a journalist, storyteller, chronicler, novelist, poet and playwright. Born in 1839, he was one of the founders of the Brazilian Academy of Letters. As a classic of Brazilian literature, he continues to be published with new editions that privilege various aspects of his production. *Mulheres de Machado* (Women of Machado) brings together seventeen short stories featuring female characters, tracing different profiles of women of the 19th century. Seen as modest, unfaithful, obedient or warriors, they are all in the condition of servility imposed by the society of that time.

Keywords: Woman. Tales. Literature woman.

¹ Synopsis of the book for the Catalog Of The Children's Book Fair 2018 Bologna. Books published in 2017 and reviewed in 2018. Review and English version: Gisele Dionísio da Silva

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